

AURORA

Aurora

Research & Innovation

Open Science Training Programme

Deliverable 6.3 -
Accompanying report

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Executive Summary

This report serves as an accompanying document to Aurora RI deliverable 6.3 - *Open Science training modules*.

This deliverable is the result of work carried out within the Aurora partner universities as part of the Horizon 2020 funded Aurora RI project.

Building on the available information and training courses at the Aurora partners that we collected for our knowledge base from Task 6.1 ([deliverable D6.2](#)), we have established Open Science training modules. These are aimed at helping students and researchers to incorporate Open Science practices into their research workflows and to become ambassadors for Open Science. In this training programme, we focus on hands-on skills, as most of the Aurora partners have general information and training courses/e-learning available for their students and staff. The Aurora Open Science Training Programme is open to all early-career researchers at the partner universities, and the educational resources for each of the training sessions are made freely available.

In this report, we describe:

- ▲ Our considerations for the training programme
- ▲ The schedule of training modules for early-career researchers at Aurora partner universities
- ▲ Future possibilities for shared training within the Aurora consortium

Project Abstract

Aurora was formed in 2016 as a consortium of research-intensive universities deeply committed to the social impact of their activities. The objective of Aurora is to match academic excellence with societal relevance. One of the core values of Aurora is to learn from and with each other and the Aurora RI project is an important part in realising this.

The Aurora RI project develops closer research and innovation support structures to complement the excellent research and innovation activities within the Aurora Alliance, a European Universities Initiative funded by the European Commission. It will further deepen and expand the cooperation between these universities and strengthen their identity as research-intensive universities dedicated to societal impact. The aim of Aurora RI is to develop a research and innovation support agenda framed by the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and based on the four priority domains of the Alliance:

1. Sustainability and Climate Change
2. Digital Society and Global Citizenship
3. Health and Wellbeing; and
4. Culture: Diversity and Identity.

The project focus is to identify and achieve an understanding of best practices and policies on sharing research infrastructure and resources, cooperation on open science and entrepreneurial activity, empowering human capital, and mainstreaming citizen engagement. Throughout the project we analyse and map best practices already in place, learning from each other. We define barriers to cooperation at national and international level and find ways to overcome them where possible. The findings will create the basis for our Research & Innovation support agenda and will be shared with the other European Universities and beyond. The actions implemented during the project period aim at creating a platform for cooperation that will sustain beyond the lifetime of the project and equip researchers and students at Aurora Alliance Universities with a broad toolkit to conduct excellent research and disruptive innovation.

Aurora RI Work Package 6: Open Science

Academia is in a transition towards a more transparent way of doing and sharing scientific research. This shift to Open Science increases the accessibility of research, which contributes to research integrity and opens new avenues for collaboration with other researchers and societal partners. In Work Package 6 of Aurora RI, we focus on *Sharing and implementing Open Science practices*. Within this Work Package, we have defined three tasks and four deliverables:

1. Building a shared knowledge base of Open Science resources, policies, and practices

In this task, meta-information about research outputs, resources, policies, experiences, and practices on Open Science are collected from Aurora partners and beyond. The meta-information for Aurora partners is aggregated into an Open Science Monitor, and the best practices are collected in a knowledge base. This knowledge base allows the Aurora partners to learn from each other's choices and experiences. It is made freely available, so others beyond the Aurora Alliance may also benefit from it.

- ▲ *Deliverable 6.1 - Open science function to the SDG dashboard*
- ▲ *Deliverable 6.2 - A shared knowledge base of Open Science resources, policies, and best practices*

2. Establish a joint training programme on Open Science

Building on the existing Aurora Open Education database and the knowledge base from Task 1, we establish Open Science training modules. These are aimed at helping students and researchers to incorporate Open Science practices into their research workflows and become ambassadors for Open Science. Topics that will be covered are Open Access publishing; how to make research data and software FAIR; how to guarantee research integrity; and how to engage with the general public about research. The educational resources for these training sessions will be made freely available.

- ▲ *Deliverable 6.3 - Open Science training modules*

3. Creation of a network of Open Science researcher communities within and between the Aurora institutions.

A network of Open Science communities is created within and between the Aurora institutions. In these Open Science communities, students and researchers who want to learn about Open Science can share experiences and inspire each other. A platform will be created in which local communities within the Aurora Alliance institutions can interact with communities from other institutions, allowing for international collaboration.

- ▲ *Deliverable 6.4 - Open Science Community starter kit and a platform for these communities to interact*

Considerations for the Open Science Training Programme

For the second deliverable of this Work Package (D6.2 - *Aurora Knowledge base on Open Science*), we collected available resources, policies, experiences, training/workshops, and practices on Open Science from the Aurora partner universities, to aggregate them into an Open Science knowledge base.

During this exercise, it became apparent that many of the Aurora universities have information and training in place on the general principles of Open Science (specifically on Research Data Management, or RDM).

Examples of existing Open Science knowledge training courses:

- ▲ RDM course (VU) - 4hrs - how to write DMP, specified for all VU faculties, at some faculties mandatory for PhD candidates
- ▲ Intro to RDM for PhD Students (CBS) - 3,5hrs - specific to Social Sciences, mandatory for PhD candidates (intro to RDM, DMPs, FAIR)
- ▲ RDM course I (CBS) - 1,5hrs - general intro to RDM, specific to Social Sciences
- ▲ RDM course II (CBS) - 1,5hrs - how to write DMP, specific to Social Sciences
- ▲ RDM course III (CBS) - 1,5hrs - how to make research data FAIR, specific to Social Sciences
- ▲ Advanced RDM (CBS) - 3,5hrs - documentation, reproducibility, data FAIRification, optional for PhD candidates
- ▲ OS course (UNINA) - 15-20hrs - for PhD candidates, specific to humanities
- ▲ Intro to RDM (UEA) - on request for staff, with a focus on digital research data, and integrated in the PhD candidates' training offerings
- ▲ RDM Curriculum (UDE) - regular offer of full-day introductory courses on RDM specialised for either STEM subjects or education, humanities, social, and economic sciences or (bio-)medicine and 2-hour advanced courses on RDM tools and practices, e.g. OSF or data reuse.

In addition to that, there are many eLearning resources, both specific to Aurora universities and more general:

- ▲ eLearning Open Access (URV)
- ▲ eLearning RDM (URV) - general
- ▲ eLearning RDM course (CBS) - general
- ▲ How to FAIR (CBS) - online resource with testimonials, practical tips, and a quiz
- ▲ [RDM kit Elixir](#) - general
- ▲ [Finnish Social Science Data Archive](#) - specific to Social Sciences
- ▲ [CESSDA](#) - Data management expert guide - specific to Social Sciences
- ▲ [Darjah](#) - specific to Arts and Humanities
- ▲ [Parthenos](#) - training catalogue, specific to Humanities
- ▲ [OPERAS](#) - infrastructure for Humanities/ Social Science

As there already are many resources on Open Science and RDM, we decided to focus on hands-on skill training for our Aurora training programme which also adds to the joint skills development framework developed in WP5 "Empowering Human Capital" of the Aurora RI

project . Specifically, we focused on training/workshops on how to use Open Science tools, and how to improve general data and software skills. Some of these training courses were already available at Aurora partners, but for others we reached out to our network.

For example, we connected to OpenAIRE^[1], with which we have a [memorandum of understanding](#) (MoU). Within this MoU, we collaborate on registering research outputs to monitor Open Science practices (see also deliverable D6.1 - the [Aurora Open Science Monitor](#) and [accompanying report](#) from this Work Package). Also part of the MoU is to include OpenAIRE services like [Amnesia](#) for data anonymisation, [Argos](#) for data management, [Zenodo](#) for data deposition, and [EpiScience](#) for setting up Open Access journals in its training courses on Open Science practices.

Schedule of training modules on Open Science

We have come up with an Aurora Open Science Training programme, consisting of the following modules:

- ▲ September 2022 (total of 96 hours, over the course of 15 weeks): **Cohort 1 of the Open Science Community Incubator** programme (see forthcoming report on deliverable 6.4)
- ▲ March 2023 (total of 96 hours, over the course of 15 weeks): **Cohort 2 of the Open Science Community Incubator** programme
- ▲ 19-21 and 26-28 September 2023: **Coderefinery workshop** on basic/intermediate level software and data skills, organized by Coderefinery.
- ▲ 14-17 November 2023 (4x 5 hours): **Software Carpentries** on basic software and data skill training (shell, git, intro to Python), organized by VU (see invitation in Annex 1 as an example)
- ▲ 29 November 2024 (2 hours): Working with the **Open Science Framework**, organized by VU/OSF
- ▲ 8 December 2023 (2 hours): **Introduction to R Notebooks**, organized by UDE
- ▲ January 2024 (total of 96 hours, over the course of 15 weeks): **Cohort 3 of the Open Science Community Incubator** programme
- ▲ 17 January 2024 (2,5 hours): **Opening up research data**, organized by OpenAIRE (including data management planning in Argos and anonymisation using Amnesia)
- ▲ 25 January 2024 (2 hours): **Data Stewardship Wizard**, organized by UPOL
- ▲ 7-9 February 2024 (4x 5 hours): **Software Carpentries** on basic software and data skill training (shell, git, intro to Python), organized by VU
- ▲ 21 February 2024 (2,5 hours): **Discover and enhance collaboration**, organized by OpenAIRE (including how to use the Aurora portal to discover useful literature and data)
- ▲ 20 March 2024 (2,5 hours): **Navigating the Open Access Publishing Venues**, organized by OpenAIRE (including Open Access routes, and how to create your own diamond Open Access journal with EpiSciences)

¹ OpenAIRE is a non-profit organisation that contains a service catalogue for sustaining Open Science information services as part of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

The educational resources for each of the training sessions are made freely available after the sessions.

Future possibilities for shared training within Aurora

Professionalisation through a shared competence framework

Most universities reinvent their own wheel of Open Science and Research Data Management training. Within this Work Package and for this deliverable, we have started to share resources, training and good practices between the Aurora partner universities. To be able to properly compare training and workshops, it is necessary to develop a shared framework of competences and learning goals that individual universities' training can be mapped onto. Within the Skills4EOSC project, such a framework of *minimum viable skillsets* is being developed. In the future, the Aurora universities can start using this framework to further develop shared training programmes on Open Science knowledge and skills.

Training for research support staff

For this deliverable, we focused on training opportunities for early-career academics (e.g. PhD candidates, postdoctoral researchers). However, as we recommend in our deliverable 6.2 - the Aurora Open Science Knowledge Base, it is important to upskill not only academic staff, but also research support staff and policy officers.

Some of OpenAIRE's services and workshops are aimed at library/ information support staff (e.g. OpenCitations for research information specialists, or OpenAPC for library content managers). Within the Aurora 2030 project, we will focus on strengthening the ties between support staff at the different Aurora universities. Joint workshops for support staff fits very well within this project.

Training for senior staff and students

For this deliverable, the training opportunities are only available to early-career academics, but not to staff and students. However, staff employees have an important role in changing the research culture in their groups towards Open Science practices; similarly, as research Master students are tomorrow's academics, they should be taught the principles of Open Science and good RDM practices as early as possible.

It is important to expand the reach of Open Science training to all Aurora academic staff and Master students through embedding of these principles in the training/educational curriculum.

Annex 1: example invitation

AURORA

Do you want to improve your software skills for research?

Join our training on

November 14th, 09:30 - 14:30 (CET)

November 15th, 09:30 - 14:30 (CET)

November 16th, 09:30 - 14:30 (CET)

November 17th, 09:30 - 14:30 (CET)

Register now!

<https://vu-nl.lib-cal.com/event/4031010>

What is this about?

This is a workshop that will help programming novices to gain fundamental software skills. The Software Carpentry workshop is a 4-half-day, hands-on training that will cover task automation via Shell, version control with Git, and basic programming and data visualization with Python!

Who should attend?

This is a hands-on course for researchers and support staff. You might find it useful if you are looking to improve your research process by learning how to program with Python and how to be in control of multiple versions of your work.

Brought to you by:

